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Research Article

Development and Characterization of a Cream Formulation Incorporating Vran Ropan Oil

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ABSTRACT

The formulation and evaluation of an herbal cream for wound healing was the goal of the current research project. Wounds are physical injuries that cause a break or opening in the skin and alter the normal structure and function of the skin. A variety of medications and formulations for the treatment of Vrana (wounds) have been described by Acharya Sushruta. In Sushruta Samhita, a formulation for healing wounds by the name of Ropana Taila is mentioned. For thousands of years, people have employed herbal treatments to heal and treat wounds. A Siddha taila known as Vranropantaila is utilized in Ayurveda to treat wounds and have anti-marking properties. There are sixteen components of herbal and mineral origin in it. It is created using a unique method that is mentioned in Ayurveda. However, due to poly-herbal formulation, it becomes difficult to standardize. The goal of the current research article is to discuss Ropana Taila's work in wound healing.

INTRODUCTION

From ancient times many herbal Ayurveda preparations have been used in the management of different types of wounds. 'Ropan Tail' is an ayurvedic preparation which has been used traditionally to promote wound healing of clean wounds. The present study was undertaken to determine the wound healing potential of Ropan tail. As it is less oily, messy and sticky, most patients find it more user-friendly. [1] Ropana

Taila is explained in Sushruta Samhita chapter 37 verse 26. [2] It's used to heal crack. It contains Harridan (Curcuma longa), Daruharidra (Berberis aristata), Devdaru (Cedrus deodara), Priyangu (Callicarpa acrophylla), Agar (Aquilaria agallocha), Tagar (Valeriana wallichii), Lodhra (Symlocos racemosa) and Til Taila (Sesamum indicum). utmost of the herbal medicines presents in Ropana Taila have katu, tikta rasa and have anti seeditious, analgesic and immunomodulatory

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action [2] “Vranaropantaila” is Siddha taila used in Ayurveda for wound healing with anti-mark potential. “Vrana” means wound and “Ropana” means healing. It is useful in the rapid healing of the wound. Vranaropantaila is a reputed Ayurvedic formulation which is used for wound healing treatment. [3] A wound is an interruption to skin integrity caused by physical trauma or disease or break of the skin that cause disturbance in the normal skin anatomy and function. [4] Wound healing is defined as a complex and elaborate biological action which start off in response to an attack on normal healthy skin. [5] The crack mending process consists of four largely integrated and lapping phases hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and towel redoing or resolution. [6] Creams are semisolid emulsions intended for application to the skin or mucous membrane. A low fat moisturizer that disappears into the skin is called as vanishing cream. It softens skin, leaving nothing behind. [7] Vanishing cream are o/w emulsion based preparations containing aqueous phase and oil phase. [8]

Types of skin creams:

There are two categories for them. Oil painting-in-Water (O/W) creams are made up of tiny drops of oil painting scattered throughout a continuous phase. Another type of oil painting-in-Water (O/W) conflation is when the oil painting is scattered as droplets throughout the waterless phase. Water-in-oil painting (W/O) creams are made of tiny water droplets scattered throughout a continuous, velvety phase. The conflation is of the water-in-oil painting (W/O) type when the dispersed phase is water and the dissipation medium is an oil painting. [9-11]

MATERIAL:

Sr no	Ingredients	Therapeutic Uses
1	Paraffin Wax	Skin softening agent
2	Petroleum jelly	Moistening agent

3	Oil	Wound healing
4	Methyl Paraben	Preservative
5	Rose oil	Fragrance

The cream was formulated using vrana ropan tail as active pharmaceutical ingredient and petroleum jelly, paraffin wax, methyl paraben, rose oil as excipients. As mentioned in Ayurvedic text Ropana Tailais used in wound healing. It has antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and analgesic action which makes it suitable to use in wound. Phytochemical constituents of ingredients of Ropana Taila also add to its Ropanaaction. [12] The vrana ropan tail used in formulation is manufactured by "Aushadhi bhavan, Ayurved seva sangh"

Fig 1. Marketed Product (Vranaropan Talia)

Petroleum has a wide range of uses in dermatology, as a carrier for medicated ointments, and a standalone treatment. Its nonflammable, non comedogenic, and rare allergic properties [13] Paraffin wax is a white or colorless soft, solid wax. It’s made from saturated hydrocarbons. It’s often used in skin-softening and lubrication.

METHOD:

Creams are semisolid formulations widely acceptable by the society. The skin is the most accessible part of the body and as such is also highly vulnerable to injuries. In case of cuts, burns and wounds, topical formulations such as creams are the most preferred for treatment and [14]

Forms of medication of creams Trituration Levigation, Fusion method We used trituration system for geometric and homogenous mixing of all the excipients and the herbal oil. The cream was prepared by using the other excipients that's, Petropetroleum jelly, paraffin wax, methyl paraben, rose oil. [15] By using trituration method, we have developed three batches of our herbal cream, namely F1H, F2H, and F3H. All three batches were evaluated for different parameters like appearance, PH, viscosity, phase separation.

Lab Work:

Trial batches:

For trial batches, dissolving cream formula was used. The cream base consists of stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, triethanolamine, sodium hydroxide, glycerin, water, incense and preservative. Both the oil and water phase was mixed at constant temperature of 70 ° c with nonstop stirring. Then the cream was allowed to cool with constant

shifting. A homogeneous cream was formulated. Upon storehouse for a period of 1 month the oil oozed out of the cream and therefore the expression was changed.

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Quantity (gm)
1	Stearic Acid	2 gm
2	Cetyl Alcohol	0.05
3	Tri ethanol amine	0.12
4	Sodium hydroxide	0.036
5	Glycerin	0.8
6	Water	6.994
7	Perfume	q.s
8	Preservative	q.s

Final formula:

A new formula of paraffin wax, petroleum jelly and preservatives, perfume was made into batches Formulation A, Formulation B, Formulation C. [15]

Ingredients	Formulation A	Formulation B	Formulation C
Paraffin wax	1.5	1.5	2.0
Petroleum Jelly	7.5	7.0	6.0
Oil (in gm)	1.0	1.5	2.0
Oil (in ml)	0.828	1.242	1.656
Methyl paraben	0.04	0.04	0.04
Rose oil	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.

Fig no 2 . Prepared Formulation (Cream)

Physical Evaluation:

Determination of pH: The pH of the cream can be measured on a standard digital pH meter at room temperature by taking adequate amount of the

formulation diluted with a suitable solvent in a suitable beaker. The pH of the cream was found to be in the range between 5-6.

Parameter	Formulation A	Formulation B	Formulation C
Colour	Oyster white	Oyster white	Oyster white
Feel	Smooth	Smooth	Not smooth

Consistency	Good	Good	Not good
pH	7.4	7.4	7.4
Spreadability (gcm/sec)	40.43	32.89	30
Viscosity (mPa.s)	1906.6	1916.6	1926.6
Tube extrudability	Excellent	Good	Good

Organoleptic properties:

Colour:

Oyster white

Odour:

Rose like

Spread ability: Adequate volume of sample is taken between two glass slides and a weight of 20

gm is applied on the slides for 10 seconds. Spreadability can be expressed as,

$$S = m \times l / t$$

Where, m-weight applied to upper slide, l-length moved on the glass slide, T-time taken.

Spreadability was found to be 33.94 gcm/sec

Reading	A	B	C
Weight	20 gm	20 gm	20 gm
Length	15 cm	15 cm	15 cm
Time	7.42 sec	9.12 sec	10 sec
Observation	40.43 gcm/sec	32.89 gcm/sec	30.0 gcm/sec
Mean	33.94gcm/sec		

*All above readings are in triplicate and SD taken

Viscosity:

Viscosity of formulated creams can be determined by using Brookfield Viscometer. Viscosity was set up to be 1916.6 mPa.s

Reading no.	1	2	3
Observation	1906.6 mPa.s	1916.6 mPa.s	1926.6 mPa.s
Mean	1916.6 mPa.s		

*All above readings are in triplicate and SD taken

Homogeneity:

The formulation was tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch and it was found to be homogeneous without any gritty particles.

Removal:

The ease of removal of the creams applied was examined by washing the applied part with tap water.

Dye test:

The scarlet dye was mixed with the cream and a drop of cream is placed in a slide and covered with

a cover slip and examined it under a microscope. The dispersed globule appeared red so the cream was confirmed as o/w type.

After feel:

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amount of cream was checked.

Type of smear:

After application of cream, the type of film or smear formed on the skin were checked.

COMPARISON OF HANDWASH WITH OTHER COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS

Sr. No	Evaluation Parameters	Formulated Cream	Marketed Cream Placentrex
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1	Colour	Pearl white	Brilliant Blue
2	Odour	Rose like	No Odour
3	Texture	Smooth	Smooth
4	Appearance and Homogeneity	Translucent	Translucent
5	Grittiness	Non-Gritty	Non-Gritty
6	Skin Irritation Test	No Irritation	No Irritation
7	pH	6.5	7
8	Foam Retention	15ml	18 ml
9	Stability	Stable	Stable
10	Viscosity	60	70

RESULT:

The oil was used and formulated 3 different formulations named F1, F2 and F3. These formulations are safe to use for skin. We have checked the various parameters of the evaluation test. After completing & checking the evaluation parameters, we have seen that the Formulation A showed good consistency, appearance, pH, no signs of phase separation, and simple removal.

Discussion: In a discussion, we've prepared a special batch of herbal cream that doesn't cause any side effects or adverse reactions using the vrana ropan oil. The herbal vanishing cream was prepared by using o/w emulsion method using mixture of vrana ropan oil, paraffin wax, petroleum jelly.

CONCLUSION:

The vanishing cream of vrana ropan oil with the best properties and having nutritional value was to be prepared by simple methods and less equipment are required. The prepared herbal cream also has anti inflammatory and antibacterial activity due to this it is used in wound healing. Further studies are required for this vanishing herbal cream. It was found that this type of formulation of the vanishing herbal cream was not prepared earlier. Oil in water emulsion-based cream was formulated using natural ingredients and was evaluated. By combining all these ingredients, it can be concluded that this cream can be used as a wound healing cream and the ingredients mixed can produce synergistic effect of the other. Further

studies can be carried out on stability and skin irritancy test of the cream.

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